

Abstract**Cutaneous Larva Migrans: A Case Report Successfully Treated with Topical Albendazole**

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Background: Cutaneous Larva Migrans (CLM), also known as "creeping eruption", is a neglected zoonotic helminthic infection with significant impact on the lives of millions of individuals living in and around the tropics. Common causative agents include *Ancylostoma braziliense* and *Ancylostoma caninum* acquired when individuals come in contact walk with soil contaminated by dog or cat faeces.

Case Report

A 23-year-old female undergraduate student was seen at the outpatient clinic of the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare, with pruritic skin lesions involving her left hand. The lesion is said to be progressing in one direction and is associated with a clear discharge at one end. She reported a history of engaging in a beach party 2 weeks before the eruptions appeared.

Physical examination revealed a serpiginous skin lesion on her left wrist extending to the forearm.

Based on the clinical characteristics and history of contact with wet sand and living in the tropics, the diagnosis of CLM was made.

Intervention and Outcome

The lesion was treated by local application of a mixture of powdered Albendazole and vaseline over seven days with resolution of lesions.

Conclusion

CLM is a neglected tropical disease and a major cause of morbidity in the tropics. Control measures should be geared towards raising awareness among local communities and healthcare practitioners, and developing treatment guidelines.

Keywords: Cutaneous Larva Migrans, Topical Albendazole, Treatment.

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